

EFFECT OF NOTCHES ON THE LOW-CYCLE FATIGUE FAILURE
OF CROSSPLY COMPOSITES

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The dominant role of the localized concentration of stress on the fatigue life of metallic structures is well understood. Results obtained with glass fiber reinforced plastics show that the composites in general exhibit a relatively small sensitivity to high magnitude localized stress fields in the high as well as the low cycle regions. This is because a delaminated region develops in the immediate vicinity of the notch and grows in size until failure finally occurs. The delaminated zone essentially changes the geometry of the notch during the fatigue process. Thus the progressive fatigue damage effectively creates a new notch which has a significantly larger radius and a lower stress concentration factor.

The behaviour of composites shows some similarities to that of metals also. In fact, the delamination may be considered as the counterpart of yielding in metals. And just as brittle metals are fully notch sensitive, there are also composites which show very little delamination and hence are more notch sensitive. In a given composite itself, the behaviour may be different in different directions. For a particular crossply composite, it has been found that in the 0° -direction there was some delamination and hence a relatively low notch sensitivity. For the same composite, in the 45° -direction there was much more delamination; and tensile specimens showed 'necking' in static as well as fatigue loading; and the notched specimens exhibited higher static and fatigue strength than the unnotched specimens.

The stress concentration factors have been determined by applying the knowledge gained recently in photo-orthotropic-elasticity.

Introduction

A great deal of experimental and theoretical development has been published regarding the effects of stress concentration on the fatigue strength of metallic materials (1,2,3,4). However, this information does not apply to composite materials which exhibit marked anisotropy and inhomogeneity. Much of the work regarding the effects of stress concentrations on the fatigue behaviour of composite materials has been performed by Boller and his associates (5). Boller has shown that the composite materials (glass fabric reinforced polyesters) exhibit very little sensitivity to notches. Dally and his associates tested crossply and quasi-isotropic laminates in which the reinforcement was not in the form of a fabric and concluded that the composite materials exhibited a relatively small sensitivity to high magnitude localized stress fields; they also proposed a relief mechanism to account for the notch insensitivity of the composites: the zone of delamination at the root of the notch due to fatigue damage grows in size as the cyclic loading of the specimen continues and the delaminated zone essentially changes the geometry of the notch during the fatigue process (6).

The conclusions of Dally et al were extended into the low-cycle region by Prabhakaran for a glass fabric reinforced epoxy material (7). He established that even though the fatigue mechanism could be different in the low-cycle and high-cycle regions, the stress relieving mechanism through delamination is effective in both the regions.

In the case of metals it is well known that brittle metals are fully notch sensitive in static and fatigue loading. Ductile metals may have a higher notched static strength compared to unnotched static strength, due to local yielding; in general the stress relief through local yielding and the strengthening effect of the high local strain rate at the root of the notch reduce the stress concentrations somewhat from their full elastic values, even in fatigue.

The aim of this paper is to investigate the notch sensitivity of different types of composite materials and verify if the generally accepted notch-insensitivity of composites applies to all composites without exception.

Materials and Test Procedure

Basically two different composite materials were employed in this study. One of these was supplied in cured form commercially and is referred to in this paper as 'material A'. The reinforcement was in the form of a woven fabric with E-glass fibers and the matrix was an epoxy resin. The composite contained 51 per cent of

glass fibers by volume, in the form of 16 layers of fabric. Each layer of fabric consisted of 53 per cent glass fibers in the warp direction and the rest in the fill direction. Two sets of specimens were prepared from material A, one set cut along the warp direction (0° -direction) and the other cut along the 45° -direction.

The second material was also fabricated from a glass fabric and an epoxy resin, but in the laboratory. The matrix material used was a relatively brittle one, with the trade name *Araldite CY230. Ten plies of glass fabric were used in the laminate and each ply was balanced in the warp and the fill direction. This composite is referred to in this paper as 'material B'. The specimens were cut along the warp direction.

All the unnotched and notched specimens were machined by using aluminium templates on a high speed routing machine. The dimensions of the specimens are shown in Fig. 1.

The stress concentration factors (K_t) associated with the orthotropic crossply materials were taken from the results of a photoelastic analysis of a side-notched (semi-circular) specimens by Dally and Alfirevich (8). The material used by these investigators was, of course, different but it was of balanced construction (properties in the warp and fill directions the same); the materials employed in this study were close to a balanced construction for the 0° -direction and so the values of K_t were considered to be a good approximation. These stress concentration factors are given in Table I.

For the 45° -orientation the K_t values were not readily available and so were determined photoelastically. The details are presented in the next section.

The static and fatigue tests were conducted on an Instron testing machine. The axial fatigue tests were performed by cycling unnotched and notched specimens between stress limits, at a cross-head speed of 0.5 cm/min. The tests were carried out in fluctuating

Table I. Stress Concentration Factors for 0° -orientation

Geometric Parameter, $2r/w$	Stress Concentration Factor, K_t
0.125	2.80
0.375	1.95
0.750	1.40

*manufactured by CIBA (India).

tension with the minimum stress equal to 5 per cent of the maximum stress ($R = 0.05$). A total of 48 specimens were tested to obtain the low cycle fatigue curves for each orientation, 12 each for the un-notched and for the three notch-size specimens. During the fatigue tests, the extension limits were also noted.

Determination of K_t Values for the 45° -orientation

Whereas the stress concentration factors for the 0° -orientation were taken from a previous reflection photoelastic analysis, the values for the 45° -orientation were obtained from a transmission photoelastic analysis. The theory of photo-orthotropic-elasticity is now established to a great extent (9,10,11). In particular, the determination of stresses on the boundaries of cut-outs is straightforward (12,13).

The model material utilized was an E-glass fiber reinforced polyester, with the matrix specially blended to produce a refractive index almost exactly equal to that of the reinforcement. The resulting transparent, birefringent composite was balanced (because of the use of a balanced fabric) with about 50 per cent by volume of fibers.

Notched specimens were machined from the photoelastic model material, with the notch parameter $2r/w$ equal to 0.125, 0.375 and 0.750. Each specimen was loaded in tension and the resulting isochromatic fringe patterns were photographed. Typical fringe patterns are shown in Fig. 2.

Whereas the location of the maximum fringe order on the notch boundary gives directly the location of the maximum tangential stress in isotropic materials, the variation of the material fringe value along the notch boundary also has to be taken into consideration in orthotropic model materials. Such variations are shown in Fig. 3, where the distribution of the tangential stress is also given. It can be seen that the stress is maximum where the fringe order is also a maximum. Once this was established for a notch, the determination of the stress concentration factors for each notch was straightforward and the results are presented in Table II. It may be mentioned that there was no residual isochromatic response (because of the balanced construction).

Table II. Stress Concentration Factors for 45° -orientation

<u>Geometric Parameter, $2r/w$</u>	<u>Stress Concentration Factor, K_t</u>
0.125	1.94
0.375	1.40
0.750	1.10

Static and Fatigue Test Results

The S-N curves were obtained for material A-0° orientation, material A-45° orientation and material B-0° orientation, both for unnotched as well as notched specimens in each case. The static strength values (taken as the fatigue strength corresponding to $N = 1$) were obtained as the average of three test results. From the appearance of the specimens after failure in the static tests, it was observed that delamination damage was minimum in the case of material B (0°-orientation) and maximum in the case of material A, 45°-orientation. Three sample unnotched specimens are shown in Fig. 4. It was also observed that the unnotched material A-45° orientation specimens exhibited a distinct 'necking' phenomenon, which is noticeable in Fig. 4.

For fatigue, the magnitude of the applied stress was adjusted to give a reasonably uniform distribution of points over a cyclic life ranging from 1 to about 1000 cycles. The unnotched and notched S-N curves for material A-45° orientation and material B-0° orientation are shown in Fig. 5. In a previous study of low cycle fatigue of fiber glass reinforced plastics, Dally had observed, on the basis of a regression analysis, that a straight line gave the best correlation besides being the simplest to use (14). Therefore best-fitting straight lines were used to represent the S-N curves in this study. It was observed, in the case of material A-45° orientation, that the notched static and fatigue strengths were consistently higher than the corresponding unnotched values; the beneficial effect increasing with the severity of the notch.

The observations from unnotched static test specimens, that delamination damage was minimum for material B and maximum for material A-45° orientation and that the latter exhibited necking, were found to be true in the case of unnotched and notched fatigue test specimens as well. Sample specimens after failure are shown in Fig. 6 and 7.

While the fatigue tests were conducted between stress limits, the variation of the extension limits as a function of the cyclic life was also noted. These variations together with the variation of the corresponding extension range are shown for unnotched specimens of material A-45° orientation and material B-0° orientation in Fig. 8. In the case of material B, the extension limits continuously but steadily increased but the extension range was remarkably stable. In the case of material A, for the 0°-orientation the same behaviour was observed (7); however, for the 45°-orientation there was a steep increase in both the extension limits initially followed by a steady increase and towards the end of the fatigue life there was again a steep increase. The extension range increased steadily throughout the fatigue life except very close to failure when there was a sudden increase.

The 'normalized' S-N curve for notched ($2r/w = 0.75$) material B specimens is compared, in Fig. 9, with the 'normalized' -N curve. While the maximum stress in the cycle was normalized by dividing it by the static tensile strength, the stabilized extension range in fatigue tests was normalized by dividing it by the ultimate extension in static tests. Thus, the strain ratio essentially becomes the extension ratio for a particular notch. The two curves are seen to be quite close together. By taking the extension ratio instead of the strain ratio, the problem of gage length was avoided; all specimens were gripped in the testing machine over the same length. For the other notches also, the same type of behaviour was observed.

The effectiveness of the notch, with its associated high amplitude localized stress field, in the deterioration of fatigue strength has been evaluated by the determination of the fatigue strength reduction factor,

$$K_f(N) = \frac{S}{S_K} \quad (1)$$

Also, the notch sensitivity was determined from

$$q(N) = \frac{K_f(N) - 1}{K_t - 1} \quad (2)$$

in order to rank the effectiveness of the notch in terms of the normalized parameter ranging from zero to one.

The changes in the notch sensitivity as a function of cyclic life are shown in Fig. 10 for all the three series of tests. The results for material A, 0° -orientation conform to the generally accepted conclusion that composite materials are relatively insensitive to notches. But the curves for material B show that the notch sensitivity can be very high for certain composites. The negative notch sensitivity values for material A- 45° orientation are the result of the notched static and fatigue strength being higher than the corresponding unnotched values.

Conclusions

Based on the test results described in the previous section, it is concluded that composite materials, for purposes of evaluating the notch sensitivity, can be subdivided into three categories: those which are capable of very little delamination (similar to material B), those which are capable of a reasonable amount of delamination (similar to material A, 0° -orientation) and those capable of extensive delamination (similar to material A, 45° -orientation). The first type of composites are almost fully notch

sensitive, the second type have a relatively low notch sensitivity and the third exhibits a strengthening effect due to notches.

For the first two types of composites the extension range stabilizes after a few cycles and stress cycling and strain cycling are equivalent in terms of fatigue life. The extension range continuously increases for the third type of composites and just before failure, the extension range increases rapidly. This behaviour is similar to the increase of temperature at certain stress levels and frequencies reported by Dally and Broutman (15).

From the behaviour of the first and second type of composites alone, one may be tempted to compare delamination in composites to yielding in metals. But the strengthening (static and fatigue) effect of notches in the third type of composites cannot be accounted for. Work is in progress to investigate this and related phenomena such as necking in composites.

Nomenclature

K_t	= theoretical stress concentration factor
K_f	= fatigue strength reduction factor
N	= fatigue life
q	= notch sensitivity
r	= radius of the notch
S	= unnotched fatigue strength at N cycles
S_K	= fatigue strength at N cycles for notch with K_t
w	= width of the specimen

Acknowledgments

This research work was supported by the Aeronautics R & D Board, Ministry of Defence, Government of India through a sponsored project. The author would like to express his appreciation to the Structures Panel of the Board.

References

1. Neuber, H., "Theory of Notch Stresses", J. W. Edwards, Ann Arbor, Michigan (1946).
2. Peterson, R. E., "Stress Concentration Design Factors", Wiley, New York (1953).
3. Kuhn, P. and Hardrath, H. F., "An Engineering Method for Estimating Notch Size Effect in Fatigue Tests on Steel", NACA Tech. Note, No. 2805 (1952).
4. Yen, S.C. and Dolan, T. J., "A Critical Review of the Criteria for Notch Sensitivity in the Fatigue of Metals", Univ. of Illinois Bulletin No. 398 (1952).

5. Boller, K. H., "Fatigue of Glass-fabric-base Laminates Subjected to Axial Loading", Forest Prod. Lab. Rept. No. 1823 B (1958); Suppl. Rept. No. 1823 C (1958).
6. Dally, J. W., Carrillo, D. and Prabhakaran, R., "Effect of Notches on the Fatigue Behaviour of Continuously Reinforced Composite Materials", Recent Advances in Engineering Science, Vol. 6, edited by A. C. Eringen.
7. Prabhakaran, R., "Notch Sensitivity of GFRP Materials in the Low cycle Region", Proceedings of the 30th Annual SPI Conference, Feb. 1975.
8. Dally, J. W. and Alfievich, I., "Application of Birefringent Coating to Glass-fiber-reinforced Plastic", Experimental Mechanics (March, 1969) 97-102.
9. Sampson, R. C., "A Stress-optic Law for Photoelastic Analysis of Orthotropic Composites", Experimental Mechanics (May, 1970), 210-215.
10. Dally, J. W., and Prabhakaran, R., "Photo-orthotropic-elasticity", Experimental Mechanics (August, 1971) 346-356.
11. Prabhakaran, R., "The Interpretation of Isoclinics in Photo-orthotropic-elasticity", to be published in Experimental Mechanics.
12. Prabhakaran, R. and Dally, J. W., "Application of Photo-orthotropic-elasticity", J. Strain Analysis (October, 1972) 253-260.
13. Prabhakaran, R., "Photoelastic Analysis of an Orthotropic Ring Under Diametral Compression", AIAA Journal (June, 1973) 777-778.
14. Dally, J. W. and Agarwal, B. D., "Low Cycle Fatigue Behaviour of Glass Fiber Reinforced Plastics", Proc. Army Symp. Solid Mech., 1970, AMMRC MS 70-75.
15. Dally, J. W. and Broutman, L. J., "Frequency Effects on the Fatigue of Glass Reinforced Plastics", J. Composite Materials (October 1967) 424-442.

Fig.1. Specimen Geometries.

2. Dark- and Light-field Isochromatic Fringe Patterns for Transparent Notched ($2r/w = 0.75$) 45° -specimen.

Fig. 3. Variation of fringe order, material fringe value and tangential stress along the notch ($2r/w = 0.75$) boundary.

4. Unnotched Specimens after Failure in Static Tensile Test:
(1) Material A, 0° -orientation (2) Material A, 45° -orientation
(3) Material B, 0° -orientation.

Fig. 5. S-N curves for material B - 0° orientation and material A - 45° orientation.

6. Unnotched Specimens after Failure in Fatigue Test:
(1) Material A, 0° -orientation (2) Material A, 45° -orientation
(3) Material B, 0° -orientation.

7. Notched ($2r/w = 0.125$) Specimens after Failure in Fatigue Test:
(1) Material A, 0° -orientation (2) Material A, 45° -orientation
(3) Material B, 0° -orientation.

Fig 8 Extension limits and extension range as a function of fatigue life for unnotched specimens.

Fig. 9 Equivalence of stress-cycling and strain-cycling in terms of cyclic life for notched ($2r/w=0.75$) specimens of material B, 0° -orientation.

Fig 10 Notch sensitivity as a function of fatigue life.